

**APPENDIX A – GUIDING QUESTIONS USED IN THE GROUP INTERVIEW
ABOUT MOBILE UX EVALUATION**

Scale	Questions
Perceived Usefulness	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Is the procedure used useful for the Mobile UX evaluation process in the Enterprise?2. Will the procedure used improve productivity in the Mobile UX assessment?
Perceived Ease	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Is the procedure used easy to apply in Mobile UX evaluation surveys?2. Is the procedure used clear and objective for Mobile UX evaluation?3. Can I use the Mobile UX assessment procedure without any problems?
Lessons Learned	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Do I intend to use such a procedure for evaluating the Company's Mobile UX?2. Based on the reality of the company, I anticipate that I will use the procedure in the Company
Future Expectations	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. In your view, what main lessons can be drawn from this moment?2. What is the main challenge in evaluating Mobile UX today at the Company as a startup?3. What is your opinion when comparing the procedure presented with the approach used previously in the Company to evaluate Mobile UX?